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SACRIFICING CHILDREN TO EMPOWER WOMEN

Vicious Feminists Agenda

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This study Article / Report is based on Legal Journals, Indian Penal code, Code of Criminal Procedure of India, Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims.

Summary: The term "SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN" covers a broad range of tactics, false litigations, abuse of children and murders of the children in the hands of their most trusted person and violent acts committed on them with the help of law, by women / Mother by using Women centric laws of India. These laws are biased against men and specially designed only for women and favor only young women.

As per National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reports and statistics almost 95% Child custody cases settled in favor of women and Fathers are forced admit and deny Custody on the threat of False Rape or other LEGAL TERRORISM cases. The exact numbers such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men / fathers are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM which stops them from meeting their children or claim custody.

Key Findings: Majority men / Fathers are not getting Custody of their children. Their request for even a visitation is denied, but they are forced to pay Maintenance. Section 17 of The Guardians and Wards Act, 1890 says "Father is the natural guardian of the minor" but that's only in Law books but not followed practically. Most Fathers are afraid to file for child custody or child visitation because it will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, false rape, out raging modesty of women or any other 50 women centric laws existing in India.

Methodology: Information for this report is sourced from various secondary sources, various News publications, testimonies, and Survey statistics etc. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the

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topic. It is an effort to not only highlight the plight of Men, but also about how the law is misused in India to violate rights of Children who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies.

Introduction: The Hague Convention is a multi-national treaty that seeks to protect children wrongfully taken away by one of the parent from the custody of the other parent.

To support Indian Women, promoted by WCD/NCW directs Government of India not to sign any such treaty as most of the time such cases of running away with children pertain to women instead of men. India is not ready to sign Hague Convention even though other countries accuse India of not adhering to any protocol with respect to international parental child abduction. 90 per cent of requests for the return of “abducted children” from other countries remained unresolved for over a year.

Indian women abduct children from lawful custody from a foreign country and come back to India and file some women centric case and manage to get LOOKOUT NOTICE (LOC) to prevent man/father from entering India to contest child custody to get access to foreign born, foreign citizen child.

But Indian Feminists twist Hague conventions terms in their own version to show it's against women / mother *“The terminology of the Convention is very offensive, labeling the removal of young kids from a country of their birth and citizen by their own parents as “abduction”. This misrepresents things when a parent (usually the mother) leaves the country taking children following breakup, divorce or separation from the opposite parent, mostly husband. The abducting parent in most cases moves to a different / home country to either protect themselves, the child, or both.*

This is the truth where India is being asked under The Hague Convention to return children from their Indian women / mother and family, and send them back to foreign-domiciled parents, or child protection agencies (cf. Article 8 of The Hague Convention, giving “any person, institution or other body” the right to claim abducted child in a member country)”. Terming that only mother is protector and all Men / fathers are abusive and rapists.

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Under the UN convention, there is no Scope for Fathers who fight for Child custody and the protection of Children & Young people from the abuse and neglect. It was formed by the child welfare / protection professionals, advocates for children, children's lawyers, researchers, academics, and parents to promote the Rights of the Children. United Nations has UN_WOMEN agency but no UN_MEN or nothing for Men.

In 2007, Ministry of Women and Child Welfare,(WCD) supported by United Nations Children's Fund, conducted a study to understand the immensity of child abuse in India, the result they found that 53.22% children faced one or more forms of sexual abuse; among them, **52.94%** of abused children are boys.

Child sexual abuse is a horrific, traumatic event in the life of a child. According to the WHO (1999), it results in real or potential harm to a child's health, development, trust, dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility and survival.

In India out of its total population, 40% are children, and India is ranked as the sixth most unsafe country for children. Among them, 47.06% are of girls, and boys are 52.94%, and among them 69% of physically abused, 88.6% were physically abused by parents. 65% of school going children reported facing corporal punishment; 50.2% of children worked all 7 days in a week and they never reported abuse to anyone. Homeless street children, poor young age working children, and children in institutional care or orphanage reported highest incidence of sexual assault.

In authors own words "I have been consulting/Advising and talking to men and his Family since 2000. I predominantly discuss in the Criminal field of Law. Until, in 2007, when I was asked to talk to a Father who was appearing in the Family Court in Bangalore. He alleged that his 3-year-old son had been brutally assaulted by the child's mother because she was angry with father of the child, when he caught her red handed with her lover. This case made me to look into a new pathway in law.

From that time onward, my life took on a new direction. I joined the Fathers rights along with Men's rights where I was asked to assist a number of fathers who had their children taken from them by the Family Court after reporting that their children had been sexually abused by their father or partner and handed to the abusive mother. I was asked to assist fathers in all States of India. For the following ten years I did my duty mostly pro-bono. It was during these Court cases that I noticed a distinct pattern of corrupt conduct of the

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Family Court whereby the fathers were treated with abuse and disrespect. They were called Alcoholic / Womanizers / liars / Cheaters / Rapists / jobless, and accused them of coaching their children to lie. The fact that very young children suffering did not move police or Child Protection Authorities into doing proper investigations into the complaint of child sexual abuse. The Family Court Judges, were more concerned with discrediting the fathers and supporting the abuser. The conduct of the court and judges in most of the cases in which I had appeared, were abominable.

*I was shocked to realize that conduct of the Family Court '**Step Mother Policy**' was an orchestrated corrupt system that was designed to discredit fathers and remove their children from them. Question is, what motivates them to act against Fathers in such an inhumane manner. Family court judges make all efforts to avoid custody to father, it's my own experience where judge asked me "**You filed custody case just to harass her right?**" My son was left with her old Parents and she went abroad. When I asked for custody, judge asked "Who is at home to look after the Child?" I replied my mother, the Judge replied back as if he is paid for it or it's his own case, "Your mother is old she can't raise a child at this age". Even her mother was also of the same age, but as per the judge that's ok. This is the bias men face in Family Court.*

*Later in same case when I approached High court of Karnataka, at Bangalore; Judge ordered Visitation on condition that I have to deposit my Passport as well as 10 Lakhs (**ONE MILLION RUPEES**) in mother's name, as I was fighting for visitation for 13 years, and have not seen my son for 13 years.*

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Learned counsel for the appellant undertakes that for the period of appellant's stay in India, he shall surrender his Passport with the jurisdictional Police Station, who shall return the same in time so as to enable the appellant, to return to his place of work.

few

ORDER COPY PASSPORT DEPOSIT AND 10 LAKHS DEPOSIT SCREEN SHOT

This shows how the family court judges are biased, Asked to deposit passport as if I am a notorious absconding terrorist and one Million is impossible for a normal person. But judge wanted to stop me at any cost, so he ordered 10 Lakhs and I deposited it within a day.

A sum of Rs.10 lakhs has been set apart and placed in Fixed Deposit in Vijaya Bank, Karkala Branch, Karnataka.

Learned counsel for the appellant states that the nominee shall be changed to Mrs. [redacted] i.e. the mother of [redacted]. He is directed to do so in order to remove any likelihood of this amount being misused by any other person. The appellant is directed to place this amount in a Cumulative Deposit for an initial period of 8 years. However, if any amount is needed for the education of

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Even that did not melt the judges stony heart, even after knowing how eager the father is to meet his son - [News details here [CLICK HERE - https://mynation.net/abio/news/](https://mynation.net/abio/news/)]

Most of the time Mother takes the child. If father files visitation/Custody appeal, visitation itself takes not less than four / five years and by then child is totally brainwashed. Once the child is no longer able to remember the father, Child is called to the court and asked, "YOU WANT TO STAY WITH MOTHER RIGHT?" The confused child will just nod with whatever the judge says because child has no option to choose with whom they can stay. This is how Visitation / custody in India is decided in the favor of the mother."

If mother fails to take the child when she leaves her husband's home, she will report to police that her child is abducted. She will not inform that the child was born and staying in father's house. She will report that the child was kidnapped by the father and kept in his house. Police will register her complaint as is and arrest the father and snatch the child and handover to the mother. Recently one of our member was also arrested by PS NIT Faridabad Haryana Police, without any verification. If father reports a similar complaint stating the mother has taken away his child, police will say that she is the mother and entitled to take her child and so no action is taken. Above this, they will mention to file an appeal for custody in the court.

In few cases, even after the father has proved that the child is not his with the help of a DNA test, the court ordered him to pay for child support. Mother can even deny Parentage testing. No family court dares to order DNA test on child so as to shield the mother.

The fathers that I have counseled are only the tip of a very large iceberg. Over the years we are talking of thousands of fathers who have been described by the Judiciary as child abuser or molesters. Many times judiciary forcibly removed a father from his child for the crime of reporting sexual abuse of his child by his wife or her partner and in some cases the grandfather. It took me some time to realize that the fathers had lost their children from the moment they filed application reporting sexual abuse. I endeavored to report the conduct of the Family Court to friends and acquaintances, but was met with disbelief and their belief that fathers lie, to stop their wife from seeing their children. I was accused of being obsessed and crazy. The Myth of lying fathers was deeply entrenched in the community.

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Not only Indian Family courts but Indian government too is against fathers. So far India has refused to sign The Hague Convention in Child Abduction.

The Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction is a multilateral treaty developed by the Hague Conference on Private International Law (HCCP) that provides an expeditious method to send back a child internationally abducted by a parent from one signatory member country to another.

Suppose if an Indian woman marries a NRI person and settles in some country, and somehow marriage goes wrong and woman returns to India with her child, here Hague convention will enter into picture and in such cases, the mother will be a “child abductor”. An application can be made to the authority in India for the return of the child to the place of “habitual residence”, that is the any other reciprocal country who has signed the convention.

One of the father approached me, who is an Australian citizen, his wife is also Indian origin Australian citizen. He found out that she is meeting another man, when questioned she took her Australian born Son and came back to India. She filed a false IPC 498A, domestic violence hiding her Citizenship status as Australian. She registered a complaint for an attempt to murder in Lucknow 5 years ago. She even named her husband’s brother though he had not visited India for the last 5 years. However, Lucknow Police registered a case on all of them without any verification. She also managed to get LOC issued, so as to stop the father from entering India to claim his Australian born son. As India has not signed Hague, he could not approach them. India is shielding such Women abductors. (Case details can be shared on request).

It is reasonable for the community at large to ask if what I am saying is correct, why is there no news about the forcible removal of fathers from their children and the children handed to their sexual abusers (Mothers Lovers)? Why is not published by newspapers / magazines or on TV? The reason is that the Family court has a complete gag order which can punish anyone who breaches this order of silence with 6 months’ jail. It is criminal contempt of the Section 12 of Contempt of Court Act, 1971.

The Chief justice of All the Family Courts, Maintains that these draconian orders are to protect children. Nothing could be further from the truth. Section 12 of Contempt of Court Act, 1971 is for the protection of Judges, select employed psychologists, and the so called Independent Child Lawyers in their immoral and illegal conduct in separating

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children from their fathers. Unfortunately, it has been difficult to raise or expose these issues of this corrupt and biased system because of a gag order in preventing them from doing so. So their conduct, favoritism towards women cannot be revealed to the general public. No radio station will report it, no newspaper / media will write / publish about it, and no TV program will cover it. They are warned off. Failure to comply can result in a jail sentence citing contempt of court. However, independent articles have started to appear about the dysfunction of the Family Court and fake complaints, false allegation by women / mothers and ill treatment of Fathers.

The NCPCR hardly presents any case against the Family Court of India or on behalf of literally thousands of fathers and children around India who have suffered no less than war crimes against humanity. You will read a number of claims against the Family Court which include: Breaches of the United Nations Rights of the Child, Denial of Natural Justice and Human Rights. The misuse of equal parenting provisions in the Family Law Act to punish fathers and allow sexual abuse by women lovers of their children. The appointment of the Independent Child's Lawyer by the Family Court to be used as a tool in supporting or proceedings against fathers, to support the mother of the child or children. Most of them have never seen the children or the father, but support the separation of the child from the primary carer. Even Indian Law books says Father is natural guardian, but it's only in law books.

For those who have had the misfortune of appearing in 'The Step Mother Policy' of the Family Court. The Independent Child's Lawyers obvious bias against fathers during the court's proceedings is patently obvious. In some cases, I would consider their conduct immoral. They cross the floor and openly support the mother. The incestuous relationship between the Independent Child's Lawyers and the Judges in removing of, or, restricting the parenting of children by their fathers, is often quite obvious.

The Court's selective appointments of psychiatrists or psychologist that are hired for the specific purpose of making false or negative reports against the fathers.

The Fraudulent reports by psychologists or psychiatrist claiming the fathers are suffering from serious mental illnesses or Alcoholic, for the purpose of removing the children from their father and handing them to their abuser. The bias of psychologists that use a template of mental disorders for the purpose of recommending to the court the removal of children from their fathers. The exorbitant fees charged by the selected psychologist as much as Rs.2500 or more for 3 one hourly interviews. It is not unusual for a father to

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have to find or asked to deposit Rs.10, 00,000 to try and protect their children from sexual abusers, only to find at the end of the day that the result was pre-determined from when the father walked into the Court and filed a restraining order complaining of sexual abuse. It is quite amazing that the Psychologists and the Family Court maintain the fathers are delusional, in addition to every known mental illness known to man, and yet these fathers have provided every last cent in legal fees to protect their children from abuse. Neither would a father lie and go to such lengths to maintain that lie.

The NCPCR charges the Family Court, with consistent breaches of the ‘Denial of Natural Justice’, ‘Breach of human rights’, and knowingly and ‘consistently committing mental torture, to fathers and children. This is a most serious statement. This claim is not uniquely an Indian problem but a world-wide problem, at least in the UK and the USA, Denmark and Ireland, where children are separated from their fathers for doing what they are mandated to do, care and protect their child.

It is the intention of the NCPCR to provide sufficient evidence to support a Legal Inquiry of the corrupt and inhumane practices of the Family Court that have brutally removed children from their fathers and sent their children to live with those who have sexually assaulted, abused or raped them. Unfortunately, it’s difficult to convince enough politicians or mandated to do, and serve the people. Unfortunately, many fathers are too scared to put pen to paper to report which attract wrath of the Family Court. Most of the time no Politicians will act against any such Personal matter unless they have VOTE BANK from the large community or some Publicity which benefit them.

We ask how in the name of humanity in the 21st century can a civil court remove a child from its primary carer (Father is Natural guardian) and hand that child to the abuser. Some have been convicted of major crimes, extra marital affairs and even her lovers are Paedophiles. Yet the Family Court would prefer the child or children to be in the hands of an abuser than a caring father.

“Most of the time Fathers are allowed for visitation on condition only if they pay Maintenance or child support” says another concerned Father Tanmoy Dutta from Calcutta.

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Needless to mention, in default of making payment, any amount as indicated hereinabove, the instant revisional application shall stand automatically dismissed and the petitioner-father shall have no visitation rights to the child.

JUDGMENT COPY OF CALCUTTA HIGH COURT ORDER

All Over the world most of the time child custody is granted to mother by default, Even if she has criminal records or is a Prostitute. There are many incidents where mother abuse or even killed children but law was never changed to grant custody to Father. If any Father is contesting and requesting child visitation or custody, his case is delayed or given date after dates. In India if women are not present in court for long custody battles spanning years, judges will not object but if father is not present they will threaten to dismiss the custody petition because of which the father travels thousands of miles every time just for the sake of the child.

Recently in Tanmoy Dutta of Calcutta case he requested virtual visitation but judge consulted the child's mother and she denied virtual visit. This shows how biased the laws are and judges favor women in custody litigations.

Children need the warmth and surroundings of their parents 24 hours a day. Neither can a mother replace the father nor can a father replace the mother. It is a universal truth that both the parents are required for healthy growth of the child / children. However with forcing equality & equating mother with father & father with mother, the various institutions of law go with very frivolous arguments which become quite illogical.

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Here I would like to share incident where child is not ready to leave his father but Police by force handover child to mother. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7mOde3-Dhlo>
(CLICK HERE TO WATCH THE VIDEO)

With the increase in cases of matrimonial disputes in the courts of India, it has become difficult to give proper & healthy upbringing to the children. For a complete multi-dimensional growth to become level-headed mature adults, a unified-family atmosphere is needed by children. Such issues are further amplified by petty matters like treating one of the parent as some kind of distant relative & asking them to pay for & submit applications for "visitation" rights, "maintenance", etc. does in no way address the real issue of 24 hour parenting. The mere thought of making one parent as basic guardian makes the child's heart deficient due to the other parent's absence in his / her life.

Though there are numerous laws for the betterment of children in Indian society, the ground reality is limited to showing concern only.

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Children go through harrowing times seeing their parents fighting and separating. The Institutions make the situation more difficult & rather painful by not having professional counseling (for all the family members of both sides) and other means to let the child understand that the family is unified for them. What the child actually sees is the long drawn custody battle in courtrooms. It affects their view of life & hampers their healthy upbringing. The real issues get side tracked for commercial gain of others. At the end of the day, the very purpose of having a family gets defeated and children's are the biggest sufferers.

Not only children suffer because of bias, we demonstrate children's are handed over to murders and many such innocent lives lost.

HERE IS THE SOME OF THE NEWS WHERE MOTHER KILLED HER OWN CHILDREN, KILLED BY PERSON WHOM THEY TRUSTED MOST.

1. Odisha woman strangles infant daughter, attempts suicide

The police have registered a case against the woman for allegedly killing her child.

A woman attempted suicide in Odisha's Ganjam district after killing her 19-month-old daughter because her husband rejected her suggestion to stay separately from her in-laws, police said.

Police said the Sabitri Gouda, wife of Kulamani Gouda from Bhiwanipur village in Ganjam district used to have frequent fights with her husband as she insisted on living away from her in-laws.

Sadar police station inspector Santoshini Oram said the couple had been married for two and a half years. But just weeks after her marriage, Sabitri started pestering Kulamani for staying away from the family. Kulamani, who worked as a mason, ignored her demand. After the birth of their daughter last year, Sabitri kept on pressuring her husband to take up separate accommodation for them which led to frequent quarrels.

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On Friday morning, when Kulamani and other family members had gone to their farmland Sabitri allegedly strangled her daughter.

“When Kulamani and others returned home at noon only they found Sabitri sobbing with her daughter lying close to her. She confessed to her crime. When she attempted to end her life by slitting her wrist, the family members rescued her and informed the police. A case of murder case has been registered against Sabitri,” said the inspector.

Ref: https://m.hindustantimes.com/india-news/odisha-woman-strangles-infant-daughter-attempts-suicide/story-QRFecF9G9xWRRoHkvd4x3O_amp.html

2. Woman held for dropping month-old daughter into water tank. She wanted a son

The woman was produced before the district court from where she was sent to jail under judicial remand.

A 21-year-old woman was arrested in Bhopal on Friday for allegedly killing her one-month-old daughter since she wanted a male child, according to the police.

The woman, Sarita Mewada, a resident of Dehriya Khajoori village of the district was arrested under Section 302 (murder) of IPC after the police found inconsistencies in her statements. She confessed to the crime later, the police said.

Deputy inspector general (DIG) of police, Bhopal, Irshad Wali said, “The father of the baby, Sachin Mewada, lodged a complaint with the Khajoori police station on Thursday about his daughter reported missing from inside his house. A police team recovered the body of the baby from inside a 500 litre water tank kept inside a room of the complainant’s house with the lid shut from the top.”

“During the investigation police got to know that the child and her mother Sarita were alone in the house when the child was reported missing by the mother,” he added.

Police interrogated Sarita Mewada and she confessed to having committed the crime.

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The DIG said, “In her statement given to the police, Sarita said she married Sachin Mewada a year ago. In August, she gave birth to a girl child but she was not happy as she wanted a boy. Sarita said her in-laws were also unhappy over the birth of the girl child. On Thursday, the baby was crying when she got upset and dropped her in the water tank. Then, she closed the lid of the tank.”

The woman was produced before the district court from where she was sent to jail under judicial remand.

Ref: https://m.hindustantimes.com/india-news/woman-held-for-dropping-month-old-daughter-into-water-tank-she-wanted-a-son/story-mztZvLwv3LSOZi2DRuP6nJ_amp.html

3. Superstitious Kalyugi mother arrested for killing 8-year-old daughter

Police have arrested a superstitious mother who strangled her eight-year-old girl in Faridabad. On Sunday, the police told that the mother had murdered the 8-year-old girl and threw her on the highway near Bhagola village in Gadwal area of Palwal.

The case is of Sanjay Colony under Mujesar police station area. An 8-year-old girl went missing under mysterious circumstances on Thursday. During questioning of the girl's parents and family, the police suspected the girl's mother. When the police checked the CCTV camera installed around the house of the complainant Rajesh, it was found that his mother was seen carrying him. After this, the suspicion of the police was deepened.

The investigation of the case was handed over to Crime Branch DLF. When the crime branch team questioned the girl's mother, she started talking like chandeliers, sorcery and sorcery. On which the suspicion of the police began to change with confidence and the police questioned the woman strictly, then the woman told that she was the one who took her child to village Bhagola in Gadwali area of Palwal and strangled her to death. She left and came home. On inquiry, the mother of the deceased 8-year-old girl told that she believes in flickering. Since 2001, he has a ghost and he has killed his daughter due to superstition.

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Ref: <https://m.livehindustan.com/ncr/story-superstitious-mother-killed-8-year-old-daughter-arrested-by-police-in-faridabad-3487107.amp.html>

4. Mom killed daughter in Anandapur: Police

KOLKATA: Six months after the death of a three-day-old girl child at Nonadanga in Anandapur, cops arrested her mother, Sonia Sen, on Sunday on charges of killing her. The autopsy report, which took five months to come due to the Covid pandemic, found light marks on the child's neck, suggesting that she might have been throttled to death.

This is the second incident in a year, in which a mother killed her newborn. The first such incident had been reported from Beliaghata.

The girl child was found dead on February 5 this year and initially, her mother claimed to have gone to the bathroom, locking the girl and her one-and-a-half-year-old boy in a room. She told cops that her daughter might have died when her son was playing with her. On Sunday, the woman broke down before the police and confessed to have killed her daughter. She was afraid that her husband, who had an illicit affair, would not support the upbringing of the girl child, said the police. "We arrested the woman after a forensic report failed to establish her accidental death theory," said joint CP (crime) Murlidhar Sharma.

Cops have registered a murder case and they will recreate the crime scene based on the woman's statement. "We need to depend on crucial forensic evidence as we do not have too much circumstantial evidence. We may seek the help of a psychiatrist to speak to the accused," said an officer.

Ref: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/mom-killed-daughter-police/amp_articleshow/77471762.cms

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5. Adampur woman held for murdering 12-year-old son

The Jalandhar rural police on Friday arrested Gurmeet Kaur, an Adampur resident, on the charge of murdering her 12-year-old son, whose body was found in the fields of Padhiana village in Adampur on September 17. A case under Section 302 of the IPC has been registered against the woman.

On the complaint of the victim's mother the police started investigation of the case. On September 24, Gurmeet's father-in-law (boy's grandfather) alleged that his daughter-in-law had murdered the boy and sought detailed investigation.

The police said during investigation the woman confessed her crime. Gurmeet lived with her three children at Padhiana village, while her in-laws lived next door in another house. Her husband Amarpreet Singh lives in Dubai. The police said the boy had seen his mother with her paramour. The boy threatened to inform his father about his mother's affair. Enraged over this, the woman killed the child. DSP Harinder Singh said, "During interrogation, her replies did not satisfy the police. She took her son to the fields, mixed sulphas tablets in the drink and hit his head with a brick."

Ref: <https://m.tribuneindia.com/news/punjab/adampur-woman-held-for-murdering-12-year-old-son-146843>

6. Shocking: Woman Took Her Own Innocent Son For Fourth Marriage, Arrested

Bihar News: Police officer told that Arun and Dharmashila got married about five years ago. But after a year she was separated from Arun. During this, Arun had demanded to keep his son Saajan with him, despite this, his devout woman separated with his child. Now the woman is accused of his murder.

In Patna, Bihar's capital, a very serious Murder in Patna case has come to light, where a mother is accused of taking the life of her own four-year-old innocent son (Mother kills her son) for her fourth marriage. The accused woman was sent to judicial custody on

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Saturday. The 23-year-old woman is accused of drowning her partially blind and speech-impaired minor son in deep water. SHO of Shahjahanpur Police (Patna Police) station in Patna district, Amarendra Kumar said that the arrested woman has been identified as Dharmasheela Devi.

Woman of only four year old innocent son killed

The whole matter is of Hasanpur Khandah village of Shahjahanpur police station area located in Fatuha on Friday. Police said the accused Dharmasheela Devi was arrested a few hours after the incident. SHO Amarendra Kumar said that the woman's son Sajan was barely four years old. She was born to the woman's first husband Arun Chaudhary after her marriage. Arun was a resident of Hilsa police station area of Nalanda.

The police officer said that Arun and Dharmashila got married about five years ago. But after a year she was separated from Arun. During this, Arun had demanded to keep Saajan with him, despite it, his religious man got separated with his child.

The child was coming in the way of the fourth marriage, so the creepy step was taken by the SHO, that the accused woman later married her second, but her husband died soon. After this, Dharmasheela married Mahesh Chaudhary, living in Mustafabad of Fatuha police station. However, Mahesh also died in a road accident two months ago. After this Dharmasheela planned a fourth marriage. However, her son Saajan was becoming a major obstacle in the person she wanted to marry. In such a situation, the accused woman killed her son. of a confession by a woman, sent to judicial custody

SHO of Shahjahanpur Police Station, Amarendra Kumar further informed that Dharmasheela was currently living in a village with her parents in Nalanda district. Bahadurchak village, which was just some distance away from his house, brought his son there and killed him on Friday morning. Not only this, after being drowned in water, he left his son's dead body there. Around 8 o'clock in the morning, some villagers saw the body of the child and reported the matter to the police. After this, the police started the investigation by taking possession of the body. In which the child's family members were found. During interrogation, the woman confessed her crime. After the FIR against him was produced in court on Saturday, from where he has been sent to judicial custody.

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Ref: https://navbharattimes.indiatimes.com/state/bihar/patna/23-year-old-woman-allegedly-kill-her-son-for-her-fourth-marriage-patna-district-bihar-sent-to-judicial-custody/amp_articleshow/78345147.cms

7. UP: woman murdered two innocent daughters when husband stopped going to maiden

A shocking incident has come to light in Jalaun district on Friday. Where a mother murdered two of her own innocent daughters due to discord in the house. Later also tried to commit suicide himself. The police has arrested the woman.

A shocking incident has come to light in Jalaun in UP. Where a mother is accused of strangling her 2 innocent daughters. Also, while trying to commit suicide himself, he injured himself by hitting his head on the wall.

After this incident, sensation spread in the whole area. The police reached the spot as soon as the incident was received and got involved in the investigation of the case. At the same time, the accused mother has been taken into custody and admitted to the district hospital for treatment.

This incident is of Chiravali village under Kotra police station area of Jalaun. Mahendra Ahirwar, a resident of the village, has accused his wife Pramila that he strangled her 4-year-old innocent daughter Mahi and 10-month-old daughter Roshni in the evening. Later, the woman herself attempted suicide and attempted suicide by hitting her head on the wall.

Woman murdered her two daughters

It is being told that the woman had a quarrel with her husband over her maternal uncle. The husband refused, saying that she had just stayed in the maiden for two months. After this quarrel, husband Mahendra went to the buffalo grazing farm and meanwhile the woman strangled and murdered both her innocent daughters and also attempted suicide herself.

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At present, the police has taken the woman into custody and she is being treated at the district hospital.

Wife was stubborn to go

The woman's husband Mahendra Ahirwar says that he had quarreled with me about going to Mayke two days ago. That slogan was going on. I along with my father went to the farm to graze the animals and my mother went to get wood. The wife was alone at home when she strangled the two girls and injured herself by hitting them head on in the wall . On getting information from the neighbors, he reached home and informed the police about the whole incident.

Police is investigating the case

The Additional Superintendent of Police, who reached the spot, said that a woman killed her two daughters. When the police reached the spot, both the girls were found dead at home. The woman was also found in an injured state. Whom is sent to the hospital for treatment. The matter is being investigated.

Ref: <https://www.aahtak.in/amp/crime/news/story/woman-murder-two-daughter-jalaun-uttar-pradesh-suicide-police-arrest-tstc-1120936-2020-08-29>

8. Tired of domestic discord, first killed the children, then the woman hanged her life

According to the police, just a few days ago the dispute of both came in the police station. Both were compromised, after which this incident has come to light.

First killed the children Committed suicide by hanging himself again

In Uttar Pradesh's village Bijnor village in Handari, a woman first killed her two innocent children due to domestic strife, then also hanged herself and committed suicide. The woman's body was found inside the house with children late at night. The woman was

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found hanging from the fan, while both the children were found dead on the bed. The incident has caused sensation in the area. police is investigating the matter.

On this incident, police say that there was a dispute between Pappu and his wife, a resident of Handari for some days. When the husband went out of the house. At the same time, the woman took this step. He first strangled two innocent children and later committed suicide by hanging them from the fan. Police has not received any suicide note.

Woman commits suicide with two children

The police have taken the bodies of the three and sent them for postmortem and started questioning the custody of the deceased's husband Pappu. According to the police, just a few days ago the dispute of both came in the police station. Both were compromised, after which this incident has come to light.

Woman commits suicide

Woman's husband detained

SP Bijnor Sanjeev Tyagi says that a woman has committed suicide by killing two of her children in village Handari. The matter is being told about domestic strife. The police is investigating the entire case. The husband of the deceased has been detained for questioning.

Ref: <https://www.aajtak.in/crime/story/suicide-woman-hang-two-children-husband-police-investigation-tstc-1109966-2020-08-08>

9. Killer Woman ...:Who strangled her husband's 6-year-old son to death

In the headline, instead of the stepmother of the killer, the killer woman is writing only because we do not have the power to write the word killer with the mother, even if she is a stepmother.

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To save stepmother, grandparents used to take Sohit to the farm every day, the child remained in the house on Friday.

A shocking incident came to light in Salempur village of Amarpur on Friday evening, where the step-mother strangled the six-year-old son to death. Step mother Suman Devi used to harass Sohit Kumar (6), son of husband Balmukund Tanti's first wife. Fearing the untoward, Sohit's grandparents used to take him to the farm, On Friday, the child remained at home due to bad luck and Suman Devi strangled him to death. As soon as the villagers came to know about the incident, people became angry and caught the woman and locked her in the house. Bhudev Tanti, the grandfather of the deceased child, told that the first wife of Balmukund Tanti died of illness two years ago. Balamukund had two twins from his first wife. In this, a child was raised to live in Maharathochak village of Kajraeli police station area. The second child Sohit lived near his grandparents. Balmukund had second marriage to Suman Devi in ??Binaud Badhari village of Bhagalpur to raise the child. On receiving the information, Banka SDPO Dineshchandra Srivastava, Amarpur Police Station Arvind Kumar Rai, Under Inspector Rajeev Ranjan, Ramashankar Singh, Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for post-mortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station. Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for postmortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station. Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for postmortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station.

Step mother Suman used to prick her thorn

After marriage, Sohit was piercing like a thorn in the eyes of stepmother. The villagers said that their grandparents used to take the child with them to the fields every day. Perhaps his grandfather and grandmother forgot to take the child to the fields on Friday, and the stepmother killed the child by strangulation. Villagers strongly condemned the incident and demanded strict punishment for the killer stepmother. The police station officer said that the accused woman has been arrested. An FIR has been lodged on the father's application.

People beating the woman if the police does not arrive soon

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There was so much anger among the villagers that if the police administration did not reach without delay, it would have been possible that people would have injured their mother by beating her. Villagers say that when its step mother reached the village after marriage, she did not want to see the child after a few days. So the grandparents used to take the child along on the farm. After Sohiti's murder, the child was left to live with father, grandparents for life.

Ref: <https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/bihar/bhagalpur/amarapur/news/who-strangled-her-husbands-6-year-old-son-to-death-127774724.html>

10. After killing, the mother threw the body of the child into the drain, arrested

In order to be separated from her husband and mother-in-law, a ruthless mother murdered her 9-month-old baby boy and threw the body into a watermill drain. The police have arrested the mother for the murder of the child. On the evening of September 7, Sudha Kujur husband Ravindra Ram, a resident of Jabala, lodged a report in the city Kotwali that in the morning she was going on foot with her 9-month-old baby in her lap. At the same time, the child had defecated near the Panchakki drain at 10 am. To clean the toilet, she was lying on the side of the drain and washing her hands. Then the child fell into the drain while stirring. Due to not finding the child, she got nervous and reached her maternal home and told her relatives about the child. On receiving the information, the body of the child, who reached near the water mill with Sudha, was found in the drain. In the PM report, the doctor said that the child's death was due to a chatter on the head. After the PM report, the police in the case of murder While registering the case, his mother Sudha Kujur is arrested. Sudha told that she took her child out of her home to go to her maternal home and murdered the child by pressing her mouth with a cloth near the water mill. After killing her, she shed the child's body in a watermill drain. However, the police have arrested the mother on charges of murder.

The mother-in-law was suspected of having an illicit relationship. During

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interrogation, Sudha revealed that she wanted to separate from her mother-in-law and her husband. Sudha's mother-in-law always doubted her relationship with anyone else. On the other hand, Susral also believed that the child did not belong to Sudha's husband Ravindra. Rather it belongs to someone else. Sudha got upset about this. Had

tried to kill even a day before,

Sudha told the police that she had tried to kill her child a day before the incident. She was beaten up on September 6 with the intention of killing her child. Because of which the baby started crying. Hearing the cry of the child, when the in-laws asked her to silence the child, she had silenced her child.

Ref: <https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/chhattisgarh/raigarh/jashpur/news/after-killing-the-mother-threw-the-body-of-the-child-into-the-drain-arrested-127761270.html>

11. This is the story of a butcher's mother

Penuganchiprolu, Jaggayyapeta village: Usha and Prasad are a couple from Manukonda village near Khammam in Telangana state. They make a living by doing masonry work. They have two children, Sukumar (4) and Ankit (18 months). Usha came in contact with Sampangi Sri alias Shiva of Ramanarsanagar, Konijar Mandal, where he was working. He has been married to her in the past. She left her husband and wife and came to Anumanchipalli village in Jaggayyapeta mandal two months ago and rented a house there. Both children stay with them. On the night of the 4th of this month, Gurai beat up Priyudi severely, outraged that the children were rioting. Beyond those blows Ankit fainted and fell and died shortly after. The children got fever. The two left in the car with the children, believing the locals that they were taking them to the hospital.

The owner asked: The two did not return the next day and the landlord became suspicious of them. In addition to the local VRVO, the police were informed. To this extent the case of Chilakallu Essay Venkateswara Rao has been registered and investigated.

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Based on the signal: Police who entered the field spotted the two and arrested them at the Suryapeta district backwaters on Wednesday based on the cellphone tower signal. The two said the original thing while interrogating in his daily style. The boy's body was admitted to the ground at Guttala near Chilukur village in Kodada zone. Police pulled out the body and conducted a postmortem. Sukumar was found to have sustained serious injuries after he was shot in the legs.

Heavy movers: Police searched the house where the two were staying and found 40 cell phones. They suspect that the accused Shiva is committing thefts of cell phones and two-wheelers.

Ref: <https://m.eenadu.net/latestnews/general/1600/120118867>

These are the few crimes committed by Mother, killing her own children.

Rest of these news can be found in below news links. these news links for last 2 months only, there are hundreds of such news where innocent children are killed in the hands of their most trusted person. **MOTHER.**

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/bihar/patna/news/woman-murdered-her-five-year-old-son-and-threw-the-dead-body-in-a-pit-filled-with-water-having-done-three-marriages-127754470.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/mp/bhopal/news/nine-month-old-girl-murdered-by-a-woman-with-boyfriend-searching-for-accused-went-missing-from-aubedullaganj-3-days-ago-127735769.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/rajasthan/bharatpur/news/step-mother-killed-8-year-old-daughter-with-poison-husband-lodged-case-127732078.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/rajasthan/bhilwara/chittorgarh/news/after-a-quarrel-in-the-couple-the-mother-jumped-into-the-well-with-her-4-year-old-son-swam-out-on-his-own-the-son-died-127724793.html>

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<https://www.india.com/hindi-news/others/women-sell-her-kid-after-husband-leave-house-4110212/amp/>

<https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/vijayawada/2019/feb/24/paramour-killed-minor-with-mothers-help-1942927.html>

<https://www.outlookindia.com/newsscroll/amp/bengal-woman-kills-2yearold-nephew-body-found-in-cupboard/1911912>

<https://www.outlookindia.com/newsscroll/amp/couple-kills-7yearold-daughter-in-ups-bareilly/1921259>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/india/article/gujarat-6-year-old-boy-abducted-murdered-after-he-saw-mother-in-compromising-position-with-lover/662643>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/woman-mother-in-law-resort-to-black-magic-sacrifice-4-year-old-boy-sentenced-to-death/639237>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/pune/article/pune-woman-murders-child-before-killing-self-as-jobless-husband-insists-on-moving-to-native-village/664273>

<https://www.amarujala.com/amp/uttar-pradesh/meerut/up-news-woman-have-arrested-in-love-affair-case-at-meerut>

<https://www.amarujala.com/amp/uttar-pradesh/aligarh/aligarh-stepmother-feeding-daughters-a-stimulant-drug-made-homosexual-relationship-aligarh-news-ali2430578106>

We have hundreds more such news links, if anyone want to verify, we can forward it.

Also refer **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>), where it explain, all the murders and crimes by Indian women. Most of the time murders of Husband.

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The paternal bond is the most beautiful and strong bond in the world. A father provides love, food, shelter and protection to a child, which is very essential for the good upbringing and overall welfare of the child. In return, a father only wants love and respect from his children. The Constitution of India gives many rights to the child and women over the property and other resources of the father or husband and also puts an obligation on a father to maintain his children and wife, but it is silent on the rights of the father over his children. Whenever a father requests for custody of his children in the event of divorce or separation, the entire Indian legal system uses all its power to prevent him from getting child custody or even visitation. It is not surprising that every day we hear news about the murder of a child by his or her own mother. In most of these cases, the innocent child was murdered by a vengeful mother to avenge the father or to hide her extramarital affair. Our Indian judiciary instead of punishing such women, frees them by saying that a mother cannot kill her child. On the other hand, our Indian judiciary imposes illogical and irrational terms and conditions on fathers to abstain their rights to meet or to care for their children. It is very difficult for anyone to find a case where an innocent child is killed by his own father.

So here a question arises that why Indian judiciary is biased against fathers?

For men, the Indian Family Court is like *Auschwitz* in India, where there is no option to survive. It is well known that the top government official or judicial officer has given a standing order to all the judges of the country to pass an order in favour of women, irrespective of the matter. As a result, most of the decisions come in favour of women and a woman gets child custody very easily even if she is by nature abusive and violent or has a criminal record. The judges easily pass an order of maintenance or alimony in favour of a woman without looking at the evidence. Even if a father is paying for the child's support, there is no governmental body to monitor the wellbeing of the child and to monitor that the money spent on a child.

It seems that handing over the child custody to the mother is the only task, for which family courts are set up. It is a misconception that child welfare is better in the hands of the mother only. This kind of thinking person always ignores the abuse and murder of the child by the mother, and it is no surprise that no one is talking about it.

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Please refer two external links in support of our claim

Fathers are better Mothers, but Mothers are not - <https://mynation.net/voice/father/>

Fathers are happier parents than mothers, new study shows -

<https://medicalxpress.com/news/2019-02-fathers-happier-parents-mothers.html>

Reference:

CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>),

Fathers being forced to agree not to contest Child custody or else face kidnap or Daughters molestation charges <https://mynation.net/voice/forced/>

SURVEY: Parent Child Access Rights <https://mynation.net/voice/pas/>

LEGAL TERRORISM IN MATRIMONIAL DISPUTES - SOLUTION FOR LEGAL TERRORISM (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3695617>)

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